

Deliverable 3.2. Structure based DL models for transfer learning trained on protein structures and 3DM data

The deliverable report D3.2 details the integration of Graph-based Neural Networks (GNNs) and Language Models into a unique platform designed for generating enhanced protein embeddings. This new platform combines information about protein structures and sequences, providing a richer and more comprehensive description of proteins, and thus enhancing the predictability of protein variants.

A central novelty of this platform lies in its integration of multiple data sources to build protein embeddings. This involves training the model with several objectives, each corresponding to a different aspect of protein structure or function, thereby enhancing the model's performance and robustness.

The platform effectively uses GNNs to model protein structures as graphs, with nodes and edges representing amino acid residues and their spatial interactions, respectively. The inclusion of these GNN representations within the framework allows it to incorporate both the primary sequence data and the 3D spatial relationships between amino acids in proteins. This provides a more comprehensive and accurate description of proteins.

Upon successful training, the model can be utilized in a framework for machine-learning assisted protein engineering. With a protein sequence and a protein structure as inputs, the model generates information-rich protein representations suitable for predicting the effects of variants on protein fitness.

In terms of broader implications, the advancements made with the platform have significant potential to improve the protein engineering process. By providing a more accurate and comprehensive description of proteins, it can facilitate the design of novel enzymes and other protein-based products. This could potentially contribute to a more environmentally friendly world by enabling the development of more efficient biocatalysts for industrial processes.